

NASA Science Mission Directorate Transform to Open Science (TOPS) **Community Panel Summary Report: November 2023**

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

In an age of digital connectivity and exponential knowledge growth, traditional forms of scientific research are undergoing a profound transformation. Open-source science, or open science, is increasingly a powerful catalyst for accelerating discovery, promoting collaboration, tackling systemic inequalities, and driving societal progress. By embracing the principles of transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility, open science has the potential to reshape the way we approach scientific inquiry and address complex global challenges. For those reasons and many more, NASA continues to explore efforts and create opportunities that promote, sustain, and advance open science via the Open-Source Science Initiative ([OSSSI](#)), Transform to Open Science ([TOPS](#)), and the Open Science 101 curriculum ([OS101](#)).

Recognizing the necessity and value of open science, NASA TOPS, a five-year program to increase the reach and visibility of open science projects, convened its final community panel in November 2023. The members of this TOPS Community Panel were scholars from various academic disciplines and public service practitioners, as well as postdoctoral researchers and graduate students. Over the course of two days, panelists provided feedback on the OS101 curriculum before its public launch, and they offered additional recommendations on ways NASA OSSSI can ensure twenty thousand people successfully complete the curriculum. Moreover, panelists proposed strategies to aid efforts by NASA TOPS to engage historically excluded communities in open science. All input will be reviewed and used to enhance NASA open science endeavors.

COMMUNITY PANELISTS:

Justin Ballenger, James Colliander, Monica Granados, Pen-Yuan Hsing, SherAaron Hurt, Logan Kilpatrick, Brian Nosek, Fernando Perez, Malvika Sharan, Qiusheng Wu

STUDENT RESEARCHER PANELISTS:

Emily Faber, Junellie Gonzalez Quiles, Sheikh Mahtab, Disha Sardana, Kylie Yui Dan

PANEL INFORMATION: AGENDA IN APPENDIX B

DAY 1: TRAINING 20K IN OPEN SCIENCE

Links to [slides](#), [video recording](#), [transcription](#).

DAY 2: STRATEGIC OPEN SCIENCE

Links to [slides](#), [video recording](#), [transcription](#).

1) KEY DELIVERABLES - SUMMARY OF PROJECT AND RESULTS (~1 PAGE)

- a) Review high-level updates and outcomes on OSSI and TOPS priorities during the “Year of Open Science.”
- b) Assess all modules within the OS101 curriculum and provide substantive feedback that can be used for future revisions.
- c) Consider outreach and engagement strategies for historically excluded communities and other groups to promote NASA open science endeavors.

2) DAY 1: TRAINING 20K IN OPEN SCIENCE (SUMMARY: MALCOLM GLOVER, EDITORS: HOLLY NORTON AND CHELLE GENTEMANN, REVIEW: STEVEN CRAWFORD, MALVIKA SHARAN, AND PEN-YUAN HSING) (~5 PAGES)

In an interconnected world, where information flows rapidly and challenges are multifaceted, advancing open science is a sign of progress. Open science is not merely a methodology; it's a transformative approach that enhances collaboration, transparency, and the collective pursuit of knowledge. At a time when global issues demand collective solutions, open science becomes a vital instrument for breaking down silos, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and ensuring that research is a shared endeavor for the expansion of scientific discoveries and the betterment of society.

A diverse group of experts assembled in Washington, D.C. for Day One of the TOPS Community Panel. The sole aim of the symposium hosted by NASA TOPS was to review and provide feedback on both the OS101 curriculum and other NASA open science priorities. The November 2023 convening marked the fourth and final gathering of the Community Panel, capping a two-year endeavor that convened diverse participants who offered valuable insights and regularly collaborated in person and online. Some of the topics covered during discussions on the morning of Day One included:

1. NASA Open Science Overview:
 - Participants reviewed joint accomplishments achieved after the federal government declared 2023 the “Year of Open Science,” collaborative efforts made possible by 16 federal agencies representing almost \$100 billion in federal research funding.

- The White House has endorsed the Open Science initiative, which involves a multi-agency effort focused on engagement, community, and outreach to the open science community.
2. White House Open Science Recognition Challenge:
 - The White House Open Science Recognition Challenge emphasizes the need for a high-profile award to demonstrate the value of open science.
 - The challenge aims to spotlight stories of open science innovation that benefit society and the teams behind them. It involves 6 different categories, ranging from citizen science to technologies enabling open science.
 - The recognition challenge is not limited to individuals but emphasizes teamwork and collaboration in open science efforts.
 3. Goals of the Office of the Chief Science Data Officer:
 - The Office of the Chief Science Data Officer at NASA is focused on implementing the strategy for data management and computing, continuous evolution of data and computing systems, and harnessing community and strategic partnerships for innovation.
 4. Open Science 101 Curriculum:
 - The Open Science 101 curriculum has been developed by teams of experts at NASA and other external partners, including an international group of open science experts.
 - The curriculum aims to reach 20,000 scientists, primarily postdoctoral researchers, and early career scientists, to establish a common language and ground rules for collaboration in open science.
 5. Curriculum Rollout Day on December 6, 2023:
 - On December 6, the curriculum will be rolled out, offering multiple ways to access it, including a self-paced online course, a book, and sign-ups for instructor-led/in-person and virtual trainings.

Discussions during the morning portion of the symposium concluded with a review of detailed plans for communications surrounding the rollout of the Open Science 101 curriculum. The primary audience for the curriculum is early career researchers, and there are concerns about the prerequisites and how they may affect enrollment. Feedback during this discussion included suggestions to make the prerequisites more inclusive and exploration of efforts to target communications for different communities (undergraduate, graduate, postdoc). The presented communication plan for the rollout of the curriculum involves detailed steps aimed at engaging diverse groups. The plan spans various

communication channels, both internal and external, with a focus on outreach, engagement, and retention. Specifically, communication feedback included:

6. Target Audience and Prerequisites:

- The primary target audience is early career researchers.
- Feedback highlighted concerns about the prerequisite stating, "experience with participating in research projects."
- Suggestions were made to make the prerequisites more inclusive, recognizing experiences like starting a PhD proposal or engaging in advanced undergraduate research.

7. Communication Channels:

- External communication channels include press releases, promotional videos, social media content, newsletters, and collaboration with different scientific societies and professional associations.
- Internal communication involves messages from leadership, NASA science center leads, and TOPS champions advocating for the curriculum.

8. Outreach to Universities:

- Efforts were made to engage with universities, targeting departmental newsletters for both undergraduate and graduate students.
- A conference for undergrad and grad students was attended to establish connections and promote the curriculum.

9. Enrollment Strategies:

- A multi-pronged approach includes a dynamic GitHub page, enrollment web page, and targeted email campaigns through the Learning Management System (LMS).
- Retention emails are planned based on user progress within the curriculum.

10. Internal Engagement at NASA:

- Internal communication involves messages from NASA's Associate Administrator, encouragement for employees to include the curriculum in their performance evaluation, and engagement of TOPS champions within NASA Centers.

11. Feedback and Reviews:

- Plans for feedback collection are in place, including the use of specific email addresses and a support system.
- The idea of gathering testimonials and promo videos from individuals who have completed the curriculum is raised as a means to boost credibility and encourage participation.

12. International Engagement:

- Efforts are being made to include an international audience, with discussions about creating "Tops Ambassadors" at universities and potentially offering funding for grad students interested in teaching the curriculum.

13. Federal Agency Collaboration:

- The conversation explores possibilities of collaboration with federal agencies and aligning the open science curriculum with existing programs, such as those targeting future graduate students.

14. Incentives for Participants:

- Ideas for incentives include competition, special town hall access, and potential collaborations with federal agencies. The challenge is to balance openness with exclusive benefits.

15. Innovative Ideas:

- Creative suggestions are made, such as integrating the curriculum into existing university programs and exploring partnerships with programs like the Berkeley Discovery Program.

16. Visibility and Promotion:

- There's recognition of the importance of a top-level, easily updatable website for the curriculum to address immediate queries and concerns.
- Suggestions are made to leverage platforms like the Chronicle of Higher Education for wider visibility.

17. Future Plans:

- Future plans include translations of the curriculum into Spanish and a focus on Minority-serving institutions.
- Ongoing evaluation and adaptation of strategies based on performance and feedback will be a priority.

Fundamentally, the beginning of Day One featured panelists and reviewers introducing themselves, highlighting their diverse backgrounds and roles at various institutions, and discussing TOPS accomplishments in 2023. Beyond remarks by in-person attendees, virtual participants also shared their perspectives, contributing to a rich and varied discussion. In the afternoon on Day One, TOPS Community Panel members and a group of graduate students and postdoctoral researchers provided detailed feedback on all modules within the OS101 curriculum. Discussions included concerns about troubleshooting technical issues with the learning modules, legal concerns, curriculum development, and the challenge of engaging diverse groups, particularly people from historically excluded communities.

During the review, several participants shared that diversity, equity, and inclusion principles should be an important part of curriculum design and communication outreach to promote OS101. The NASA curriculum development team expressed a commitment to monitoring demographics and metrics to ensure equitable access. Strategies for outreach, group accountability, and leveraging partnerships with existing organizations are also explored. In terms of ensuring NASA meets the goal of getting 20,000 people to complete OS101, participants discussed strategies for motivating individuals through personalized problem-solving approaches and there were conversations about the use of NASA branding and logos on the final certificate to encourage course completion. Existing programs like virtual cohorts and summer schools are acknowledged, highlighting ongoing efforts to spark interest in the open science curriculum. Moreover, challenges in reaching enrollment goals are acknowledged, stressing the need for adaptability. Over the course of the afternoon, conversations were collaborative and dynamic, showcasing a commitment to addressing challenges, fostering inclusivity, and exploring innovative strategies to achieve key NASA goals and advance open science practices. Moreover, Day One set the stage for strategic planning and informed decision making that can benefit future enhancements to the OS101 curriculum.

3) DAY 2: STRATEGIC OPEN SCIENCE (SUMMARY: MALCOLM GLOVER, EDITORS: HOLLY NORTON AND CHELLE GENTEMANN, REVIEW: STEVEN CRAWFORD, MALVIKA SHARAN, AND PEN-YUAN HSING) (~2 PAGES)

Day Two of the TOPS Community Panel Symposium began with presentations and conversations about NASA's Open-Source Science Initiative (OSSSI), which included details on policy and governance, coordinating core data and computing services, internal and external priorities, community engagement, and support for advanced technologies like artificial intelligence. Portions of preliminary conversations centered around the interplay between high-performance computing (HPC) and cloud technologies, with a focus on finding ways to integrate and collaborate in this space. There was also an exploration of the tension between the two technologies and the need for interoperability.

The strategic open science discussion continued with conversations about establishing a common language for open science, examining broad engagement strategies for diverse communities, and shedding light on the challenges and opportunities within the open science landscape. Some of the practical strategies for community engagement included: leveraging influential figures to promote open science and collaborating with Minority Serving Institutions to enhance the visibility and acceptance of open science practices among historically excluded groups.

Open science is inherently inclusive, transcending barriers and bringing diverse groups into the fold. Learning about open science becomes a catalyst for connection and understanding, particularly in the realm of diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility. By embracing open science principles, individuals from different backgrounds find common ground, creating an environment where varied perspectives are not only acknowledged but

actively sought. This connection-building aspect of open science learning is foundational for creating a research community that reflects the diverse tapestry of the global community.

To share the open science curriculum with the broader public, strategic steps must be taken. First and foremost, panel participants highlighted the need for ensuring the OS101 platform is user-friendly and incorporates interfaces that aid for accessibility. Using social media and community workshops can further disseminate information about the curriculum and aid improve course completion rates. Panel participants also stressed the importance of collaborating with educational institutions, community organizations, and industry partners to embed the curriculum in diverse learning environments. Encouraging partnerships with influencers and thought leaders would amplify the reach, making the curriculum a widely embraced resource for those seeking to engage with open science.

Day Two of the TOPS Community Panel provided valuable insights into the challenges and strategies for promoting open science adoption. The engagement strategies discussed, such as leveraging influential figures and connecting with marginalized populations, offer practical approaches to fostering a culture of open science. Moreover, the panel's contributions contributed significantly to advancing NASA open science initiatives and shaping future interventions. Over the course of two days, participants explored diverse topics, strengthened processes for collaboration, gathered feedback, and made sure current strategies and future goals align with NASA open science priorities.

4) CONCLUSIONS (SUMMARY: MALCOLM GLOVER, EDITORS: HOLLY NORTON AND CHELLE GENTEMANN, REVIEW: STEVEN CRAWFORD, MALVIKA SHARAN, AND PEN-YUAN HSING) (~2 PAGES)

The collaborative review of the OS101 curriculum by a diverse panel of global experts, graduate students, and postdoctoral researchers, as well as in-depth assessments of the design for every module, represented a pivotal step towards enhancing the educational content's effectiveness and relevance. By harnessing the collective expertise, insights, and perspectives of individuals across various stages of their professional and academic careers, this comprehensive evaluative approach ensured that the curriculum would resonate with a broad audience and address the diverse needs and challenges encountered by individuals who seek to employ open science practices. Moreover, TOPS Community Panel members engaged in an iterative process of review and deliberation to expedite edits to the modules and they provided other recommendations that were implemented and ultimately supported efforts by NASA officials to facilitate future curriculum improvements, while also fostering a culture of transparency, collaboration and shared decision making. All Community Panel convenings cultivated a supportive ecosystem where knowledge exchange and skills development contributed to the promotion of inclusive, and impactful scientific practices on a global scale.

Involvement of graduate students and postdoctoral researchers in the final TOPS Community Panel served as a reminder that the embrace of open science principles by

higher education and academic institutions is imperative in shaping the researchers and scholars of tomorrow. By developing an open science curriculum and finding ways to share those trainings with academic institutions and the broader public, NASA is creating opportunities for institutions to equip students and stakeholders with cutting-edge research practices, while also instilling the ethical considerations associated with transparency and data sharing. This integration is crucial for creating a scholarly environment and scientific paradigm that values collaboration and appreciates the collective nature of scientific progress. Embracing open science fosters a spirit of innovation, encouraging students, researchers, and practitioners to explore new methodologies, technologies, and modes of communication. Moreover, open science aligns with the broader societal shift towards openness and inclusivity, preparing people to be ethical and responsible contributors to scientific knowledge and discovery.

Fundamentally, the importance of the OS101 curriculum and advancing open-source science cannot be overstated. NASA recognizes that open science is part of humanity's collective journey towards a more informed, collaborative, and equitable future. The open science curriculum is not just an educational tool; it's a vehicle for empowerment, a bridge for connections, and a catalyst for positive change. As we reflect on this final TOPS Community Panel conversation, it's evident that the initiatives NASA embarks on in 2024 and beyond will pave the way for a more inclusive, transparent, and collaborative scientific community in the future. Conversations about open science must continue, for they are the threads that weave the fabric of a future where knowledge knows no boundaries and is accessible to all.

5) [CREDIT AUTHOR STATEMENT](#)

Please note the section (last name and what you worked on (original text, edits, figures, comments, organization...)).

Day 1 and 2: Glover, original text. Norton, Gentemann, edits. Crawford, Sharan, Hsing, Gentemann, Norton, comments. Glover, organization.

6) [APPENDIX A: EMAIL](#)

TOPS Community Panelists,

Thank you for participating in our November meeting. Final edits to the summary report are due by February 23, 2024 and we need your help to complete this task. Please add your comments and corrections directly to the Google document linked below. The panel summary does not require consensus and we encourage you to work together to create constructive guidance. The slack channel can be used to collaborate and, if meetings are needed, we are happy to help coordinate them. We will link the Panel Summary Report to a message on the slack channel.

Instructions:

1. Please provide your [ORCID](#) in the [update document](#) so that we may give credit for your participation in this [Google document](#).
2. We ask that volunteers review all sections of the report, make corrections, add comments, and provide additional content when necessary. All updates can be made in the main report or the [update document](#). Please put your name in the document in the section heading where it says '(Volunteer Name)' before making contributions to the main document. Be sure to add links to important resources in the appendices.
3. The link to the Panel Summary report outline can be found [here](#) in the update document. We are looking for comments on revisions to the Open Science 101 curriculum and strategies for promoting the curriculum with historically excluded communities and Minority Serving Institutions in 2024 and beyond.

We've provided resources to assist in your analysis – recordings, transcripts, and the slide decks. The Panel Summary outline includes suggestions for content and length.

What happens next:

It is important that you meet the 2/23 deadline to help inform decisions on future TOPS activities. We will upload the panel summary report to Zenodo, CC-BY license, and post to GitHub as part of the record of this meeting.

If you have any questions or are unable to participate in this editing and review process, please reach out to malcolm.e.glover@nasa.gov and holly.e.norton@nasa.gov . Thank you for supporting NASA Transform to Open Science!

All the best,

The TOPS Team

7) [APPENDIX B: DAILY RECAP](#)

Day 1: Training 20K in Open Science

<i>Tuesday, November 14th, 2023</i>		
<i>Time (ET)</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>	<i>Presenter</i>
9:00 AM	Review of Agenda and Code of Conduct	Holly Norton
9:05 AM	Introductions	Chelle Gentemann
9:15 AM	Welcome	Chelle Gentemann
9:30 AM	OCSDO Update	Steve Crawford

9:45 AM	Open Science 101 Intro and Roll Out	Amanda Adams
10:15 AM	Coffee Break	
10:30 AM	Modules Review	Postdocs and Panel
12:30 PM	Lunch	
1:30 PM	Open Science 101	Diana Ly
1:45 PM	Maintaining and Transforming OS101	Paul Bremner
2:00 PM	Question and Answer Session	
2:30 PM	Open Discussion	Paul Bremner
3:15 PM	Coffee Break	
3:30 PM	Next Steps with TOPS	Paul Bremner
4:00 PM	Open Discussion	Holly Norton
5:00 PM	Day 1 of Panel Ends	

Day 2: Strategic Open Science

Wednesday, November 15th, 2023		
Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter
9:00 AM	Introduction and Review Code of Conduct	Holly Norton
9:05 AM	Honoraria Q&A	NRESS
9:15 AM	OCSDO Open Science	Steve Crawford
9:30 AM	Open Science and Historically Excluded Communities	Malcolm Glover
10:30 AM	Coffee Break	
10:45 AM	Future Ideas Open Discussion	Chelle Gentemann
12:00 PM	Lunch/Transportation to EEOB SYOS-Panel Joint Meeting	
1:00 PM	SYOS Activities	SYOS Co-chairs

2:00 PM	Discussion	Panel Discussion
3:00 PM	Day 2 of Panel Ends	

8) APPENDIX C: RESOURCES

Below is a list of resources that were provided by panelists and participants during the three-day meeting.

Open-Source Science Initiative (OSSI)

The [OSSI](#) is part of NASA's long-term commitment to building an inclusive open science community over the next decade. Through its endeavors, OSSI is committed to the open sharing of software, data, and knowledge (algorithms, papers, documents, ancillary information) as early as possible in the scientific process.

Transform to Open Science (TOPS) GitHub Site

The [TOPS GitHub](#) site provides information on the TOPS mission and NASA's efforts to rapidly transform agencies, organizations, and communities to an inclusive culture of open science. TOPS is part of NASA's [Open-Source Science Initiative](#).

Open Science 101 Curriculum (OS101)

The [OS101](#) curriculum supports everyone's path to a more open and equitable scientific future. The curriculum aims to introduce learners to a nuanced understanding of open science, enabling participants to actively participate in open science. The five modules introduce participants to the definitions, tools, and resources available to share their research process and products more openly.

Year of Open Science

NASA, the [White House](#) and other [Federal Agencies](#), declared 2023 the "Year of Open Science," highlighting actions across the federal government throughout 2023 to advance national open science policy, provide access to the results of the nation's taxpayer-supported research, accelerate discovery and innovation, promote public trust, and drive more equitable outcomes.

GitHub Tutorial - Beginner's Training Guide

A [tutorial on how to use GitHub](#) to create new repositories, clone repositories locally, commit changes and manage project files.

Version Control with Git

[Version Control with Git](#) is a lesson on keeping track of what you've done and to collaborate with other people. Every large software development project relies on it, and most programmers use it for their small jobs as well. And it isn't just for software: books, papers, small data sets, and anything that changes over time or needs to be shared can and should be stored in a version control system.

Articles

[Why NASA and federal agencies are declaring this the Year of Open Science](#) by Chelle Gentemann in Nature